

ENHANCING ACTIVE LEARNING THROUGH BAAMBOOZLE IN CLASSROOM LESSONS

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Abstract. This article defines developing active learning through Baamboozle in classroom Lessons. Traditional teaching methods can sometimes lead to decreased student engagement and interest, particularly in grammar and vocabulary instruction. This study explores the effectiveness of Baamboozle, an interactive online platform, in enhancing students' motivation and comprehension through game-based learning. The study concludes that game-based learning fosters a dynamic and enjoyable learning environment, leading to better retention and application of linguistic concepts. Baamboozle, therefore, proves to be a valuable digital tool in modern language education.

Keywords: Game-based learning, Baamboozle, interactive learning, student engagement, digital learning tools, gamification in education.

1 Introduction

The way learning material is modified and presented can significantly impact its comprehensibility, especially if the learning process is monotonous and unengaging. contemporary educational materials can be quite tedious, leading to a decline in student interest. Traditional teaching methods can exacerbate this problem. Consequently, interactive learning tools, particularly game-based platforms, can offer an effective solution for students. This approach offers several advantages, including improved concentration, development of logical thinking and decision-making skills, quick problem-solving abilities, increased student engagement, and reduced stress levels.

Moreover, such interactive methods can enhance students' enthusiasm and motivation for learning. The game-based learning approach aims to prevent monotonous and boring lessons by creating a fun and interactive learning environment for students. Studies have shown that using games in education makes lessons more enjoyable and effective. Gamification is widely used in various fields, including education. Its main goal is to motivate and engage students in learning activities. The use of online games in the learning process is closely related to technological advancements.

Baamboozle game-based learning method increased student engagement in lessons and helped them better understand and apply grammar concepts and vocabulary as well. Baamboozle is an online platform that enables the use of games in the educational process. It offers a wide range of games, allowing students to use ready-made activities or enabling teachers to create their own customized tasks. This ensures that the content library expands daily, as teachers can upload their materials to the platform. Baamboozle is a free online platform that can be used in both offline and online lessons. Its convenience lies in the fact that students can access the platform and participate in games from anywhere using their devices.

Baamboozle is an interactive tool used in the classroom for activities like bell ringers, check-ins, or material review, fostering an engaging learning environment. This free platform allows teachers to find ready-made games or create their own. Baamboozle can also be used as an ice-breaking activity to prepare students mentally before class and focus their attention.

Baamboozle helps cultivate a spirit of healthy competition among students, develop their teamwork skills, and enhance creative thinking. Working in groups allows students to exchange ideas, work on new concepts, and foster creativity. Additionally, Baamboozle features like earning or losing bonus points make the learning process more exciting and dynamic. This game tool also positively impacts students' ability to set goals and achieve them. Today, computers, smartphones, and the internet have become integral parts of

our lives. The development of information and communication technologies has paved the way for a broader approach to education.

In this regard, new pedagogical methods are emerging by utilizing active teaching techniques in educational processes. Integrating game elements into learning significantly enhances comprehension levels. For instance, it increases students' engagement during lessons, which positively affects the learning process. Recent studies show that online games conducted during lessons positively influence students' motivation. Gamification allows educators to present ordinary problems and tasks in an interesting and exciting manner.

Therefore, games play a crucial role as a modern approach to education.

2 Methods

After registration, teachers can log into their accounts, use pre-made questions, or create new ones. On the left side of the page, there is a blog and news section that contains useful articles, game collections, and updates. In the "Class Pin" section, teachers can create a special code or organize a game without a code.

Assignments are displayed on the right side of the screen, while a search panel is located on the left. Through this panel, teachers can quickly find the required game, select the language and sorting method, and determine when the game was created. Once the teacher starts the game, they can display the tasks or hide the answers.

Snakes and Ladders. When a student gives a correct answer, a random dice roll is generated, and their marker moves automatically. Students can move forward or backward by a few steps. This game can be played individually or in teams. Snakes and Ladders helps students develop logical thinking, calculation skills, and teamwork abilities.

Story Dice. Students must create a word or sentence based on a specific topic by looking at random dice rolls. Teachers can adjust the number of dice. This method is effective in enhancing vocabulary and text construction skills. Most importantly, there is no limit to the number of participants.

Four in a Row. In this game, each participant takes turns answering questions. When they give a correct answer, circular marks appear on the board. If four circles in a row are filled, the participant earns points or a bonus. This game improves learning efficiency through visual reinforcement.

Tic Tac Toe. This is one of the most engaging games for students. They are divided into two groups and answer questions. If they answer correctly, an "X" or "O" is placed. To win, three marks must be aligned in a row, column, or diagonal. This game helps develop logical thinking, quick decision-making, and teamwork in a competitive environment.

Memory Game. This game enhances students' memory and logical thinking skills. Participants take turns flipping cards and finding matching images or words. If they match correctly, they earn points, and the corresponding image remains on the board.

Bingo. Bingo is one of the most popular games, helping students learn words and concepts. Each participant receives a bingo card and marks the correct answers. When a row or column is fully completed, the student declares "Bingo!" and wins.

When this game was used during practical lesson, in the first time, all learners reacted positively to the game-based learning method, as evidenced by their active participation and enthusiasm in the lessons. Enthusiasm is a crucial factor in English language learning, significantly impacting students' academic achievement. Students who expressed positive attitudes towards the game-based learning method actively participated in class activities and were involved in answering questions. However, some students hesitated to provide grammar-related answers, which could be attributed to their insufficient grasp of the material. In the second time, all students embraced the game-based learning method enthusiastically and enjoyed all the learning activities. This, in turn, is an important factor that facilitates their achievement of learning objectives. Baamboozle made the learning process more engaging. The result of the lesson showed that all learners actively answered grammar questions and no longer hesitated as before. This suggests that their grammar proficiency and engagement had improved significantly. It means that the use of Baamboozle in grammar instruction and in vocabulary learning positively impacted students' interest. This suggests that Baamboozle-based grammar activities encouraged students to participate more actively. Students stated that this method was highly suitable for developing grammar skills, noting that the competitive environment created by Baamboozle increased their interest.

3 Conclusion

Baamboozle is an effective tool for making the learning process interactive and engaging. By incorporating game elements, student participation and motivation can be significantly increased. This

platform enables teachers to transform traditional teaching methods and make the learning experience more efficient and memorable for students. Therefore, Baamboozle is recommended as an effective digital learning tool to boost student interest in lessons. Furthermore, Baamboozle helped students grasp various grammatical concepts, learn to write accurately and correctly, and improve their focus in class. The results indicate that the game-based learning methodology makes the grammar and vocabulary learning process effective and enjoyable.

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